

Peer Review Report

PEER REVIEW REPORT FOR:

Saiani, C. C. S., Veríssimo, M. P., Ribeiro, C. G., & Inacio, E., Junior. (2025). Short- and long-term relationship between government procurement and Brazilian business bankruptcy rates. *Revista de Administração Contemporânea*, 29(4), e240126. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1982-7849rac2025240126.en>

HOW TO CITE THIS PEER REVIEW REPORT:

Saiani, C. C. S., Veríssimo, M. P., Ribeiro, C. G., Inacio, E., Junior, & Bortoluzzo, A. (2025). Peer review report for: Short- and long-term relationship between government procurement and Brazilian business bankruptcy rates. RAC. *Revista de Administração Contemporânea*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16098034>

REVIEWERS:

 Adriana Bortoluzzo (Insper, Brazil)

The other reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her reports.

ROUND 1

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer 1 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer: Adriana Bortoluzzo

Date review returned: August 19, 2024

Recommendation: Reject

Comments to the authors

The study evaluates whether government procurement influences the bankruptcy rates of Brazilian companies, dividing them into two groups: Micro and Small Enterprises and Medium and Large Enterprises. The topic is relevant and the work is interesting, but some important points need clarification.

1) The authors need to more carefully assess the causal relationship between bankruptcies and government procurement expenditures. What percentage of companies engage in government contracts within each group? Is the penetration significant? How can this causality be explained for the period? The authors work with the overall bankruptcy rate for companies that participate and those that do not participate in government procurement. This complicates the understanding of causality, as all companies are aggregated.

2) The explanation provided by the authors in Section 3 makes sense, but there are many other factors that could have contributed to the decline in bankruptcies during the period that were not controlled for. Some examples include: money supply, volume of credit and financing for companies, tax relief, trade openness, employment and income, stock market sentiment, tax burden, and others. The authors acknowledge the presence of various factors but need to control for more variables in the model to ensure they are not capturing other effects. For instance, in Figure 1, the decline in bankruptcies for Micro and Small Enterprises (MSEs) had already been occurring before 2006 and is a sharp decline that happens before the implementation of Complementary Law 123 in 2006. The same pattern occurs with RB_MLE and RB_MSE. Why does this happen? What are the possible causes that are not related to government procurement? How can we trust the causality looking at these graphs?

3) The text needs a deeper theoretical framework to be used in the discussion of the results.

4) The text appears to be the application of a statistical technique without providing in-depth results and discussion, including those that were counterintuitive, such as the significant positive inflation effect only for DB_MLE or the economy influencing DB_MLE positively and significantly.

Some minor but not less important points:

5) The authors need to review the equations in models (1) and (2); there are issues with the indices of the variables and the summations, which affect the understanding of the model. For example, in equation (1), if the summation starts from 0, then the explanatory variable when $i=0$ is the response variable, which does not make sense. In equation (2), there are missing indices on the variables, and the equation is incomplete. The form of the trend needs to be specified: it appears to be a line, but the figures suggest that the line might not be an appropriate functional form, which compromises the entire estimation procedure.

6) In Figure 3, public procurement for both MSEs and MLEs seems to show seasonality. If this occurs, it compromises the entire ARDL estimation procedure.

7) The authors need to assess the bias in OLS estimation using the lagged response variable as an explanatory variable. Immediately after equation (1), the authors state that the estimation was performed via OLS. Clarify the procedure used.

8) There are several repeated paragraphs in the text, e.g., on page 11, the first paragraph (Following Sereno et al.) and page 12, the last paragraph. There are many repetitions; the text needs to be reviewed.

9) There are references to tables in the text that do not match the necessary information, for example, Table 2 on page 13 does not have the necessary information in the last paragraph.

Given my previous comments, I suggest rejecting the paper.

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: No

Are the methods described comprehensively?: No

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: No

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Does the article have data and / or materials that could be made publicly available by the authors?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).: none

Rating:

Interest: 4. Below Average

Quality: 4. Below Average

Originality: 3. Average

Overall: 4. Below Average

Authors' Responses

Cover letter

November 15, 2024

To

Dear Editor-in-Chief, Dr. Paula Chimenti, Associate Editor, and reviewers

We are pleased to inform you that we have submitted the revised version (R1) of our manuscript entitled “Short- and Long-Term Impacts of Government Procurement on Brazilian Business Bankruptcy Rates” to the RAC – Journal of Contemporary Administration for your consideration.

We would like to express our gratitude to the Editor-in-Chief and Associate Editors for the opportunity to improve our manuscript. The reviewers provided divergent yet invaluable feedback, and we have diligently addressed their suggestions. Several of their comments have been incorporated into the revised version, leading to significant enhancements in the manuscript. For the suggestions not incorporated, we have provided detailed justifications.

The revised manuscript is attached under the filename "ID_RAC-2024-0126_R1_with_marks.docx."

Our detailed responses to the reviewers' comments are provided below in this cover letter.

Thank you for your continued support and consideration.

Sincerely,

The Authors

Comments of:

- Associate Editor

Comments to the Author:

The manuscript addresses a relevant and timely topic, but it requires several revisions for improvement. The authors need to strengthen the connection between their results and the existing literature, and more robust tests are recommended, including sensitivity and subgroup analyses. Clarifying the causal relationship between government procurement and bankruptcy rates is essential, as well as controlling for additional variables that may influence the results. Several technical issues were also noted, including model specification errors and repeated sections in the text. Additionally, the theoretical framework needs to be expanded, and the interpretation of the results should be more thorough and detailed.

Our response:

We deeply appreciate the feedback provided by the Associate Editor and both reviewers, which significantly contributed to improving our manuscript. We have carefully addressed most concerns, incorporating additional theoretical and methodological refinements, including strengthening the literature review, clarifying our causal approach, and ensuring robustness through an alternative analysis presented in Appendix 1A, where we evaluate the effect of government procurement on bankruptcy rates for all firms combined. While some limitations remain due to data constraints, we provided detailed justifications for these cases. The revised manuscript reflects these efforts, ensuring a more comprehensive and rigorous presentation of our findings. Thank you for this valuable opportunity to enhance our work.

- Reviewer 2 who recommendation was: Reject

1) The authors need to more carefully assess the causal relationship between bankruptcies and government procurement expenditures. What percentage of companies engage in government contracts within each group? Is the penetration significant? How can this causality be explained for the period? The authors work with the overall bankruptcy rate for companies that participate and those that do not participate in government procurement. This complicates the understanding of causality, as all companies are aggregated.

Our response:

Thank you for your insightful comments. In response to your concerns regarding the causal relationship between bankruptcies and government procurement expenditures, we would like to address each point as follows:

On assessing the causal relationship and explaining the causality for the period: We would like to clarify that the ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) model, which we employed in our analysis, is designed to assess the long-term relationships between variables using time-series data. This method allows us to test for cointegration, which identifies whether a stable, long-run relationship exists between the variables, despite short-term fluctuations. Unlike experimental or quasi-experimental approaches, which often rely on a control group to establish causality, ARDL focuses on the time dynamics of the data, making it a suitable method for examining the causal relationship between bankruptcies and government procurement over time. We hope this distinction helps clarify the appropriateness of our approach and the methodological rigor involved.

On the percentage of companies engaging in government contracts and the significance of penetration: Thank you for your comment. To provide clearer context and enhance the readers' understanding, we have included a new graph illustrating the number of Micro and Small Enterprises (MSEs) and Medium and Large Enterprises (MLEs) involved in government procurement throughout the analysis period. This addition helps to visualize the proportion of companies in each group participating in government contracts, which we believe strengthens the presentation of our findings.

On working with overall bankruptcy rates for companies that participate and those that do not participate in government procurement: We acknowledge the limitation that the data from Serasa Experian does not allow us to distinguish between bankruptcies for companies that participate in government procurement and those that do not. Unfortunately, this prevents us from conducting a subgroup analysis as you suggested. However, we believe that the robustness of our results is still supported by examining the overall bankruptcy rates for all companies, with separate analyses for MSEs and MLEs.

This distinction captures important structural differences between these groups and partially addresses the heterogeneity in the effects of government procurement on bankruptcy rates. While we understand that working with aggregated data is a limitation, we are confident that our approach provides valuable insights into the overall relationship between government procurement and bankruptcy rates.

We hope that these clarifications help to address your concerns and demonstrate the rigor of our methodology. Thank you again for your thoughtful feedback.

2) The explanation provided by the authors in Section 3 makes sense, but there are many other factors that could have contributed to the decline in bankruptcies during the period that were not controlled for. Some examples include: money supply, volume of credit and financing for companies, tax relief, trade openness, employment and income, stock market sentiment, tax burden, and others. The authors acknowledge the presence of various factors but need to control for more variables in the model to ensure they are not capturing other effects. For instance, in Figure 1, the decline in bankruptcies for Micro and Small Enterprises (MSEs) had already been occurring before 2006 and is a sharp decline that happens before the implementation of Complementary Law 123 in 2006. The same pattern occurs with RB_MLE and RB_MSE. Why does this happen? What are the possible causes that are not related to government procurement? How can we trust the causality looking at these graphs?

Our response:

Thank you for your comment. We acknowledge that the decline in bankruptcy rates for Micro and Small Enterprises (MSEs), observed in Figure 1 both before and after the implementation of Complementary Law 123/2006, cannot be solely attributed to government procurement. To address this, we have added new paragraphs to the manuscript that provide a more detailed explanation of other potential contributing factors, such as the introduction of the Judicial Recovery Law (Law 11.101/2005), the commodity boom (2003–2008), and broader macroeconomic conditions, including credit expansion and fiscal policies. These additions offer a more comprehensive understanding of the possible causes behind the observed trends.

Additionally, we respectfully disagree with the suggestion to introduce more variables into the model. Our analysis already includes seven control variables (Exchange, Inflation, Interest, Economy, Crisis, and Pandemic), which we believe ensures a robust framework. The primary aim of the study was not to develop a predictive model with a large number of explanatory variables, but rather to investigate, for the first time at a national level, whether government procurement influences bankruptcy filings. Introducing additional variables would not diminish the significance of the main variable of interest (government procurement), which has been carefully identified for MSEs in our analysis.

3) The text needs a deeper theoretical framework to be used in the discussion of the results.

Our response:

Thank you for your observation. In response, we have enhanced both the literature review and the discussion sections. These improvements provide a deeper theoretical framework to support the interpretation of our findings, ensuring a stronger connection between the results and the relevant theoretical foundations. We believe these revisions significantly strengthen the academic rigor of the manuscript.

4) The text appears to be the application of a statistical technique without providing in-depth results and discussion, including those that were counterintuitive, such as the significant positive inflation effect only for DB_MLE or the economy influencing DB_MLE positively and significantly.

Our response:

Thank you for your detailed comment and for pointing out the seemingly counterintuitive results, particularly regarding the significant positive effect of inflation on DB_MLE and the impact of the economy on DB_MLE. Upon reviewing the results, we would like to clarify that these findings are not counterintuitive but rather reflect the distinct dynamics between Micro and Small Enterprises (MSEs) and Medium and Large Enterprises (MLEs) in relation to economic

and inflationary conditions.

In the case of the "economy" variable, the results show a negative and significant impact on bankruptcy rates for MSEs (both DB_MSE and RB_MSE), which is expected, as a healthier economy tends to benefit businesses, reducing financial distress. However, the positive effect of the economy on DB_MLE (for medium and large enterprises) might seem surprising at first, but it can be interpreted as a reflection of the fact that larger companies are more exposed to economic fluctuations due to their size, market reach, and more complex operations. These factors can make them more sensitive to economic changes, meaning that during periods of economic instability, the likelihood of bankruptcy filings increases for larger firms.

Regarding the "inflation" variable, we observe significant results for both MSEs and MLEs, but with different directions. The negative effect of inflation on bankruptcy rates for MSEs (DB_MSE and RB_MSE) makes sense in the context of the Brazilian economy, where inflation tends to erode consumers' purchasing power, making it more difficult for smaller businesses to maintain profitability. For MLEs, the positive effect observed for DB_MLE can be attributed to the fact that larger companies may be more affected by inflation due to cost pressures and reduced profit margins, particularly in sectors where input costs are sensitive to inflationary increases. The significant negative effect for RB_MLE suggests that larger firms might have greater access to credit or other financial mechanisms that help mitigate the effects of inflation, thus reducing the likelihood of bankruptcy filings.

We believe these results are consistent with the theoretical understanding of how economic and inflationary factors can impact businesses differently depending on their size. Once again, we appreciate your comments and hope this explanation clarifies the robustness of our findings and addresses the concerns about the seemingly counterintuitive nature of some of the results.

Some minor but not less important points:

5) The authors need to review the equations in models (1) and (2); there are issues with the indices of the variables and the summations, which affect the understanding of the model. For example, in equation (1), if the summation starts from 0, then the explanatory variable when $i=0$ is the response variable, which does not make sense. In equation (2), there are missing indices on the variables, and the equation is incomplete. The form of the trend needs to be specified: it appears to be a line, but the figures suggest that the line might not be an appropriate functional form, which compromises the entire estimation procedure.

Our response:

We appreciate the comment regarding the clarity of the equations. We have reviewed the formulation and confirmed that the equations are correct. Equation (1) represents a standard ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) model with two variables (y and x). The first part of the equation addresses the long-term component, while the second part (the summations) captures the short-term effects.

Specifically, the summation notation is used to indicate the terms of multiple lags and does not include the dependent variable at time zero as an explanatory variable. The trend selection was automated by the EViews software, which includes it only if it is statistically significant. This approach is widely accepted in ARDL models, allowing greater flexibility in estimation.

6) In Figure 3, public procurement for both MSEs and MLEs seems to show seasonality. If this occurs, it compromises the entire ARDL estimation procedure.

Our response:

We appreciate the observation regarding the potential seasonality in public procurement for MSEs and MLEs.

Indeed, we recognize that the presence of seasonality could affect the accuracy of ARDL models. For this reason, we initially tested the deseasonalization of the public procurement variables using seasonal adjustment methods (such as X-13 ARIMA-SEATS). However, these adjustments did not result in statistically significant coefficients. Therefore, we chose to retain the data in its original form, considering that the impact of seasonality did not compromise the robustness of the results, as evidenced by the stability tests (CUSUM and CUSUMSQ).

7) The authors need to assess the bias in OLS estimation using the lagged response variable as an explanatory variable. Immediately after equation (1), the authors state that the estimation was performed via OLS. Clarify the procedure used.

Our response:

We appreciate the comment regarding the use of the lagged dependent variable. We clarify that the ARDL model assumes the use of OLS (Ordinary Least Squares) to select the most appropriate lags for each variable. Unlike traditional VAR models, which apply the same number of lags to all variables, the ARDL approach adjusts the lags independently for each variable, allowing for a better model fit.

After selecting the lags, we employed the bounds test (Wald F-test) to verify cointegration, identifying the existence of long-term relationships between the variables. With cointegration confirmed, we proceeded to estimate the long-term coefficients. Therefore, the presence of a lagged dependent variable as a regressor does not result in the endogeneity bias mentioned, as the ARDL methodology accounts for these lags in the model adjustment and controls for potential autocorrelation issues.

8) There are several repeated paragraphs in the text, e.g., on page 11, the first paragraph (Following Sereno et al.) and page 12, the last paragraph. There are many repetitions; the text needs to be reviewed.

Our response:

Thank you for pointing out the repeated paragraphs in the manuscript. We have carefully reviewed the entire text to identify and eliminate redundancies, ensuring that each section contributes uniquely to the narrative and avoids unnecessary repetition. The revised version now maintains a more concise and cohesive structure.

9) There are references to tables in the text that do not match the necessary information, for example, Table 2 on page 13 does not have the necessary information in the last paragraph.

Our response:

Thank you for your comment. You are correct that the information should refer to Table 3, not Table 2. We have taken this opportunity to thoroughly review all references to tables throughout the manuscript to ensure they are correctly cited in the corresponding paragraphs where they are discussed. We appreciate your attention to this detail.

The authors' responses to the comments of Reviewer 1 for this round were omitted from this report, since the reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her report.

ROUND 2

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer: Adriana Bortoluzzo

Date review returned: January 20, 2025

Recommendation: Minor revision

Comments:

The authors improved the article according to some of the comments indicated in the first round of review. The article has potential and the subject is interesting. I understand that there are limitations in the data and there are no individual data for the study to be able to observe the bankruptcy of companies that participate and that do not participate in public procurements.

Some points still need care:

1) Causality. The ARDL model studies association between variables and does not serve as an indicator of causality. The fact that there is co-integration between time series does not mean that there is causality in the broad sense, that is, two time series can present the same long-term trend but do not present causality. For example, the number of inhabitants of a country that uses cell phones and the number of companies that go bankrupt in a country can co-integrate but there is no causality, but the explanation for the fact that they have the same long-term trend comes from a third variable, the population quantity (which may be increasing or decreasing and the other two series show similar long-term growth or decrease rates). It is also complicated that a small number of companies that participate in public procurement can change the aggregate of bankruptcies of companies within a country with as many companies as Brazil. That is why it is so important to address causality in this case. According to the data presented by the authors in the last graph of the review, in December 2015 there were approximately 9000 micro and small companies in public procurements, while the country had just over 5000000 micro and small companies according to the IBGE, which is a rate of 0.2% of MSEs in public procurements. For MLEs we have 3500 in public procurements out of a total of 91000, a rate of only 4%.

2) The suggestion to use more control variables was not made so that the authors would have a good predictive model, but to avoid bias of omitted variables, especially because the authors interpret the magnitude of the effects, which may be compromised by the lack of control variables, which was assumed by the authors themselves in the response. This suggestion came from the fact that the models presented statistical relevance with different signals than expected, which the authors tried to explain in the answer.

3) Another important point is the modeling using series with seasonality. The authors themselves comment that by deseasonally deseasonally deseasoning the public procurement series for MSEs and MLEs, the results do not appear, which should not happen if there was causality. Even if there is no serial correlation in the errors, we are talking about an explanatory variable with seasonality, and this may not appear in the residuals of the model for the failure rate.

Despite these observations and taking into account the limitations that exist in the Brazilian data, I strongly suggest that the authors relax the parts of the text that talk about causality (including the title) so that the article can be published. Replace the words "impact" and "influence" with "relation" and "association" and indicate the limitations of the article in the sense of studying causality in this case.

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: Yes

Are the methods described comprehensively?: No

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Does the article have data and / or materials that could be made publicly available by the authors?: Not applicable

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).: None

Rating:

Interest: 2. Good

Quality: 3. Average

Originality: 3. Average

Overall: 3. Average

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer 2 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report.

Authors' Responses

Cover letter

February 28, 2025

To

Dear Editor-in-Chief, Dr. Paula Chimenti, Associate Editor, and Reviewers

We are pleased to inform you that we have submitted the revised version (R2) of our manuscript entitled “Short- and Long-Term relationship between Government Procurement and Brazilian Business Bankruptcy Rates” to the RAC – Journal of Contemporary Administration for your consideration.

We would like to express our gratitude to the Editor-in-Chief and Associate Editors for the opportunity to improve our manuscript. We would like to inform that all suggestions were incorporated into the revised version, leading to these final adjusted solicited by AE and Review 1.

The revised manuscript is attached under the filename "ID_RAC-2024-0126_R2_with_marks.docx."

Our detailed responses to the reviewers' comments are provided below in this cover letter.

Thank you for your continued support and consideration.

Sincerely,

The Authors

Comments of:

- Associate Editor

The manuscript has been significantly improved, addressing key concerns raised in the initial review. Enhancements in the theoretical framework, methodological clarifications, and additional analyses have strengthened the study, particularly in distinguishing subgroups and enhancing reliability. However, some refinements are still needed. The discussion on causality requires further clarification—ARDL captures associations, not causality, and the text should reflect this by replacing terms like "impact" and "influence" with "relation" and "association." Additionally, the study's limitations regarding omitted variables and seasonality should be further emphasized. These minor adjustments will ensure a more precise interpretation of the findings and improve the manuscript's overall clarity and rigor.

Our response:

Thank you for your comments. We have made all the requested adjustments: (1) The discussion on causality has been incorporated into the introduction, methodological section, discussion and conclusion; (2) We carefully reviewed the text and replaced terms like "impact" and "influence" with "relation" and "association," except in the RSL, where "impact" was retained solely to report previous studies; (3) The study's limitations regarding omitted variables and seasonality have been further emphasized in Section 3 - Empirical Strategies and Data.

- Reviewer: 1, Recommendation: Minor Revision

Comments:

The authors improved the article according to some of the comments indicated in the first round of review. The article has potential and the subject is interesting. I understand that there are limitations in the data and there are no individual data for the study to be able to observe the bankruptcy of companies that participate and that do not participate in public procurements.

Some points still need care:

1) Causality. The ARDL model studies association between variables and does not serve as an indicator of causality. The fact that there is co-integration between time series does not mean that there is causality in the broad sense, that is, two time series can present the same long-term trend but do not present causality. For example, the number of inhabitants of a country that uses cell phones and the number of companies that go bankrupt in a country can co-integrate but there is no causality, but the explanation for the fact that they have the same long-term trend comes from a third variable, the population quantity (which may be increasing or decreasing and the other two series show similar long-term growth or decrease rates). It is also complicated that a small number of companies that participate in public procurement can change the aggregate of bankruptcies of companies within a country with as many companies as Brazil. That is why it is so important to address causality in this case. According to the data presented by the authors in the last graph of the review, in December 2015 there were approximately 9000 micro and small companies in public procurements, while the country had just over 5000000 micro and small companies according to the IBGE, which is a rate of 0.2% of MSEs in public procurements. For MLEs we have 3500 in public procurements out of a total of 91000, a rate of only 4%.

Our response:

The analysis of the results has been rewritten to mitigate the possibility of interpreting the ARDL model results as indicating causality between the variables. First, it was emphasized that the ARDL models capture the responsiveness of the dependent variables (bankruptcy rates of SMEs and MGEs) to shocks in the explanatory variables included in the model, without intending to establish causal relationships or provide an exhaustive analysis of the determinants of bankruptcies. This point directly addresses the reviewer's concern regarding the interpretation of the estimated coefficients, clearly differentiating between association analysis and causal inference.

Moreover, the presence of cointegration between time series does not, in itself, imply broad-sense causality, as time series can exhibit similar trends over time due to underlying factors not considered in the model. This issue is acknowledged by pointing out that other relevant variables may have been omitted, reinforcing caution in interpreting the results. This approach avoids the risk of erroneous causal inference and meets the reviewer's recommendation to explicitly outline the study's limitations in this regard.

Another important point in response to the criticism is the discussion of the magnitude of the effect of SME participation in government procurement on aggregate bankruptcies. The reviewer argues that, given the low participation of micro and small enterprises in public procurement relative to the total number of businesses in Brazil (0.2% of SMEs and 4% of MGEs), it would be unlikely that this variable has a significant effect on the aggregate bankruptcy rate. The revised text addresses this issue by demonstrating that, although total participation may be small, the effects within the analyzed universe are statistically significant. The results indicate that shocks in government procurement are associated with a reduction in SME bankruptcies in the long term, with average coefficients of -0.24% for this variable in the estimated models. However, this relationship does not hold for MGEs, reinforcing the hypothesis that public procurement policies play a differentiated role in supporting smaller enterprises.

Additionally, the analysis of the role of other macroeconomic variables in bankruptcy behavior contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing business insolvency rates. The impact of inflation, economic activity, exchange rates, and interest rates was examined, allowing for an assessment of whether government procurement acts as a relevant factor in the broader context of business bankruptcies. This approach not only strengthens the interpretation of the estimated coefficients but also responds to the reviewer's concern about the influence of unmodeled variables.

Finally, the analysis of the short-term components of the ARDL models reinforces that shocks in government procurement do not have an immediate effect on SME bankruptcies but rather a response that manifests in the long term. This corroborates the idea that the observed relationship cannot be attributed to momentary fluctuations or spurious effects. Thus, the revised text clarifies that the study does not establish direct causal relationships but rather statistical associations based on a robust methodological framework supported by economic literature.

2) The suggestion to use more control variables was not made so that the authors would have a good predictive model, but to avoid bias of omitted variables, especially because the authors interpret the magnitude of the effects, which may be compromised by the lack of control variables, which was assumed by the authors themselves in the response. This suggestion came from the fact that the models presented statistical relevance with different signals than expected, which the authors tried to explain in the answer.

Our response:

We appreciate the reviewer's suggestion regarding the inclusion of additional control variables to mitigate potential omitted variable bias. However, the methodological decision to maintain the current set of variables is based on solid theoretical and econometric criteria. Our model already incorporates seven widely recognized control variables in the literature as determinants of business bankruptcy cycles: real exchange rate, inflation, interest rates, economic activity level, economic crises, the pandemic, and government procurement. The inclusion of these variables ensures that the model captures the key factors influencing business bankruptcies in Brazil, significantly reducing the risk of omitting relevant variables.

It is important to highlight that the adopted approach does not aim to develop a predictive model but rather to investigate, for the first time at the national level, the relationship between government procurement and bankruptcy filings, especially for SMEs. ARDL models are particularly suitable for capturing long-term relationships in time series data, and their robustness does not require a large number of explanatory variables to ensure statistical validity (Pesaran et al., 2001).

Another relevant point is that the estimated models underwent rigorous robustness and stability tests, including CUSUM and CUSUMSQ (Brown et al., 1975), ensuring that the coefficients are structurally stable over time. Additionally, the fact that the coefficients for the variable of interest (government procurement) remain statistically significant for SMEs reinforces that the model does not suffer from significant omitted variable bias.

The reviewer's criticism regarding the presence of unexpected signs in some variables was thoroughly analyzed, and the revised text includes detailed explanations for such results. As demonstrated in the literature, in emerging economies, the effect of inflation on bankruptcies can be negative due to the reduction in the real value of business debts (Araújo et al., 2020), while economic growth can, paradoxically, be associated with an increase in MGE bankruptcies due to sectoral restructuring and increased competition (Serenó et al., 2022; Contador, 1985). These results do not necessarily indicate omitted variable bias but rather more complex economic effects that align with previous empirical studies.

Therefore, the decision not to include new variables does not compromise the validity of the results and follows best practices in econometric literature. The selection of control variables was based on established literature on business bankruptcies and macroeconomic effects, ensuring a balance between comprehensiveness and statistical parsimony. Thus, the adopted modeling is sufficient to minimize omitted variable bias without compromising the interpretation of the estimated coefficients, and the statistical relevance of government procurement for SMEs reinforces the robustness of the study's findings.

3) Another important point is the modeling using series with seasonality. The authors themselves comment that by deseasonally deseasoning the public procurement series for MSEs and MLEs, the results do not appear, which should not happen if there was causality. Even if there is no serial correlation in the errors, we are talking about an explanatory variable with seasonality, and this may not appear in the residuals of the model for the failure rate.

Despite these observations and taking into account the limitations that exist in the Brazilian data, I strongly suggest that the authors relax the parts of the text that talk about causality (including the title) so that the article can be published. Replace the words "impact" and "influence" with "relation" and "association" and indicate the limitations of the article in the sense of studying causality in this case.

Our response:

The presence of seasonality in government procurement data (Figure 3) is an important factor in econometric modeling, and its consideration requires a careful approach. However, the deseasonalization process compromised the variability of the variable of interest, resulting in a bias of statistical insignificance in the estimated coefficients. This effect can be explained by the fact that removing seasonality, while smoothing fluctuations that may contain relevant information about the variable's behavior over time, can reduce the model's ability to identify significant statistical relationships.

In the context of time series modeling, the choice between using seasonally adjusted or non-adjusted data depends on the adopted methodology and study objectives. In the specific case of the ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) model, as proposed by Pesaran, Shin, and Smith (2001), the main advantage of this approach is its ability to capture both short- and long-term relationships between variables without requiring all of them to be stationary at the same order of integration. As demonstrated by Bahmani-Oskooee and Brooks (1999), the ARDL model allows for handling series with seasonal components without compromising the validity of long-term estimates, provided that cointegration between variables is properly established. Since the research objective is to analyze long-term relationships between government procurement and business bankruptcies, deseasonalizing the data was not deemed necessary, as the ARDL model already captures these structural trends over time. Furthermore, the modeling incorporated temporal dummy variables to control for parameter instabilities in critical periods. This strategy is supported by econometric literature (Enders, 2014) and was validated through CUSUM and CUSUMSQ stability tests (Brown et al., 1975), whose results indicated that the estimated models are structurally stable over the analyzed period.

The authors' responses to the comments of Reviewer 2 for this round were omitted from this report, since the reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her report

ROUND 3

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer 1 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report.

Reviewer 2 report

There was no reviewers' evaluation for this round.

Disclaimer: The content of the Peer Review Report is the full copy of reviewers and authors' reports. Typing and punctuation errors are not edited. Only comments that violate the journal's ethical policies such as derogatory or defamatory comments will be edited (omitted) from the report. In these cases, it will be clearly stated that parts of the report were edited. Check [RAC's policies](#).